

Effect of temperature variation on acoustic and thermodynamic properties in the multicomponent system of heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane at 298, 308 and 318 K and suitability of different theories of sound speed

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Abstract : Densities, viscosities and sound speeds of heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane system have been investigated at three different temperatures. These experimental values are used to compute few derived properties of the ternary mixture like intermolecular free length (L_f), isentropic compressibility (K_s), acoustic impedance (Z) and internal pressure (π_i). Further these parameters are used to evaluate excess parameters of the system, since excess parameters are better measure of intermolecular interactions. The excess values are then fitted into Redlich-Kister polynomial equation to estimate the standard deviation. Different theories of sound speed are applied on the system under study to validate the experimental data on sound speed and to determine the theory which is the best suited for the system.

Keywords : Thermodynamic properties, ternary mixture, acoustic.

In recent years, noticeable importance has been given to study the behavior of non-electrolytic liquid mixtures because of their wide employment in industrial processes¹. Density and related properties have been extensively studied for binary mixtures from both theoretical and experimental point of view. However, experimental data and investigations on volumetric, viscometric, acoustic and thermodynamic behavior of mixtures containing more than two components are quite scarce in the literature². So it seems useful to derive these excess parameters and to attempt some interpretations of the results for ternary mixtures.

Results and discussion

The experimentally measured density (ρ), sound speed (u) and viscosity (η) are used to evaluate derived properties like intermolecular free length (L_f), isentropic compressibility (K_s), molar volume (V), acoustic impedance (Z), internal pressure (π_i) and excess parameters by using well-established relations³.

$$L_f = \frac{K}{u\rho^{1/2}}, K_s = \frac{1}{u^2\rho}, V_{\text{mix}} = \frac{x_1M_1 + x_2M_2 + x_3M_3}{\rho_{\text{mix}}},$$

$$Z = u\rho, \pi_i (V_f)^x = K$$

where x is a constant. It is evaluated by finding the slope of the family of straight lines obtained from the slope of $\log (1/V_f)$ against $\log \pi_i$. The value of this relationship is

presented by the equation $\pi_i V_f^x = K$ is checked and verified.

Excess parameters have been calculated from following equation: $Y^E = Y_{\text{mix}} - (x_1Y_1 + x_2Y_2 + x_3Y_3)$. All the excess parameters are fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation to estimate the adjustable parameters⁴:

$$Y^E = x_1x_2x_3 \sum_{i=0}^2 A_i (1 - 2x)^i, \text{ where } x_1, x_2 \text{ and } x_3 \text{ are}$$

mole fractions of all the three components of the system respectively, A_i is the smoothing coefficient and Y^E represent the theoretical excess functions. The standard deviation was evaluated by using the following relation:

$$\sigma(Y^E) = \left[\frac{\sum (Y_{\text{obs}}^E - Y_{\text{cal}}^E)^2}{n - p} \right]^{1/2}$$

where n is the total number of experimental points and p is the degree of fitting ($p = 3$ in present case).

The internal pressure for pure liquids and their binary liquid mixtures are calculated using the relationship as given below⁵:

$$\pi_i = bRT \left[\frac{k\eta}{u} \right]^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M_{\text{eff}}^{7/6}}$$

where b stands for cubic packing which is assumed to be 2 for liquids, k is dimensionless constant which is independent of temperature and nature of liquids and its value is 4.28×10^9 , R is gas constant, T is absolute temperature and M is effective molecular weight.

Excess enthalpy and Gibb's free energy of binary liquid mixtures are given by :

$$H^E = x_1\pi_{i1}V_1 + x_2\pi_{i2}V_2 + x_3\pi_{i3}V_3 - \pi_{im}V_m$$

$$G^{*E} = RT [\ln \eta_{mix}V_{mix} - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2 + x_3 \ln \eta_3 V_3)].$$

The theoretical values of sound speeds are evaluated using the following relationships. Sound speed is calculated using the following formula⁶.

$$u^{FLT} = \frac{K}{L_{f \text{ mix } \rho \text{ Exp}^{1/2}}$$

where K is Jacobson's constant depends only on temperature and $L_{f \text{ mix}}$ is intermolecular free length of mixture.

The empirical formula for sound speed in binary liquid mixtures can be written as⁷ :

$$u^{NOM} = \left[\frac{x_1 R_1 + x_2 R_2 + x_3 R_3}{x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2 + x_3 V_3} \right]^3$$

where x , R and V represents mole fraction, molar sound speed and molar volume. Suffix 1, 2 and 3 represents the system components respectively.

Vandael Vangeel ideal mixing relation is computed from the following formula⁸ :

$$\left[\left(\frac{1}{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2 + x_3 M_3} \right) \left(\frac{1}{u^2} \right) \right] = \frac{x_1}{M_1 u_1^2} + \frac{x_2}{M_2 u_2^2} + \frac{x_3}{M_3 u_3^2}$$

where x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are mole fractions and u_1 , u_2 and u_3 are sound speeds of components of the system. The sound speed in the mixture is given by Impedance Dependence Relation as⁹

$$u = \frac{\sum r_i Z_i}{\lambda_i \rho_i}$$

The experimentally observed values of density at 298, 308 and 318 K are 816.1, 807.1 and 795.3 kg m⁻³ respectively at zero mole fraction and similarly at one mole fraction the values are 679.5, 671.0 and 662.0 kg m⁻³. Viscosity values at $x \sim 0.0000$ are 5.2454×10^3 , 3.4737×10^3 and 3.1723×10^3 Nm⁻²s and at $x \sim 1.0000$ the values are 0.3068×10^3 , 0.2004×10^3 and 0.1602×10^3 Nm⁻²s respectively. The observed sound speed val-

ues at $x \sim 0.0000$ and $x \sim 1.0000$ mole fractions are 1386.8, 1324.7, 1275.4 and 1132.0, 1097.0, 1051.6 ms⁻¹ respectively at 298, 308 and 318 K. These observed values are used to compute some derived parameters i.e. acoustic impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (K_s), intermolecular free length (L_f) and internal pressure (π_i) for the system under investigation. The values of Z , K_s , L_f and π_i at zero mole fraction are 11.3175×10^5 , 10.6919×10^5 and 10.0001×10^5 Rayl; 6.3715×10^{-10} , 7.0602×10^{-10} and 7.9526×10^{-10} m²N⁻¹; 0.5190 , 0.5563 and 0.6010 Å; 1.9045×10^3 , 1.6889×10^3 and 1.6314×10^3 atm respectively at 298, 308 and 318 K. Similarly at $x \sim 1.0000$ the respective values for 298, 308 and 318 K are 7.6919×10^5 , 7.3608×10^5 and 6.9615×10^5 Rayl; 11.4846×10^{-10} , 12.3841×10^{-10} and 13.6597×10^{-10} m²N⁻¹; 0.6968 , 0.7368 and 0.7877 Å; 0.6696×10^3 , 0.5018×10^3 and 0.4689×10^3 atm. As the mole fraction of heptane increases in the system, u , η , ρ , Z and π_i , decreases whereas K_s , and L_f increases at all the three investigating temperatures. The signs of excess parameters play a vital role in assigning the compactness due to molecular rearrangement and the extent of molecular interactions in multicomponent liquid mixtures. Fig. 1 shows the variation of ΔK_s , $\Delta \eta$, L_f^E , V_f^E , Z^E and ΔU for the system heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane. Negative deviations of ΔK_s , $\Delta \eta$, L_f^E , V_f^E and positive deviation in Z^E and ΔU parameters indicate strong intermolecular interactions which include charge transfer, dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole interactions and interstitial accommodation. Reversal of the signs of these parameters at $x \sim 0.44$ mole fraction are indicative of weakening of interaction due to dispersion forces coming in play. For the system under investigation the variation in the signs of the following parameters is former type leading to strong intermolecular interaction. In general a minimum (or maxima for Z^E and ΔU) is observed at approximately $x \sim 0.44$ mole fraction of heptane. This negative increase could be due to dipole-induced dipole interactions between 1-dodecanol, heptane and cyclohex-

Fig. 1. Variation of deviation in isentropic compressibility (ΔK_s) with mole fraction of heptane in heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane system at (♦) 298, (■) 308 and (▲) 318 K.

ane. Also there is possibility of interstitial accommodation of planar cyclohexane and tetrahedral molecules of n-heptane into 1-dodecanol self associates due to large difference in their molar volumes. Upto $x \sim 0.44$ mole fraction of heptane a decrease in ΔK_s , $\Delta\eta$, L_f^E , V_f^E , V_f^E is observed but thereafter the value of ΔK_s , $\Delta\eta$, L_f^E , V_f^E , V_f^E increases probably due to higher concentrations of heptane leads to dissociation of self association of 1-dodecanol, as well as the concentrations of 1-dodecanol reduces continuously to facilitate interstitial accommodation and dipole-induced dipole interactions. Generally, in ternary systems less interaction occurs because the addition of third component decreases the energy of interaction and the system tends to show ideal behavior. Our results are in accordance with some earlier observations with ternary and quaternary systems¹⁰. Negative variation of deviation in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) has also been observed in some systems¹¹.

The variation of excess Gibb's free energy of activation of viscous flow is depicted in Fig. 2 over the entire range of composition and temperature. The variation of G^{*E} is entirely negative at all the three temperatures taken

Fig. 2. Variation of excess Gibb's free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) with mole fraction of heptane in heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane system at (♦) 298, (■) 308 and (▲) 318 K

for investigation and the small magnitude of G^{*E} indicates the lowering of interaction between the components.

The H^E values are negative throughout the entire composition. The variation of excess internal pressure (π_1^E) over the entire range of temperature and composition is entirely positive with maximum values at mole fraction $x \sim 0.77$. The variation of $\log V_f$ versus $\log \pi_1$ at 298, 308 and 318 K are all linear. The experimental values of sound speed alongwith theoretically predicted values for Free Length Theory (FLT), Impedance Dependence Relation (IDR), Nomoto's Relation (NOM), Vandeaal Vangeel ideal mixing relation (VAN) at zero mole fraction are 1386.8, 1386.8, 1336.2, 1367.2 and 1195.4 ms^{-1} respectively at 298 K. Similarly at 308 K the values are 1324.7, 1324.7, 1283.6, 1312.0 and 1150.1 and 318 K 1275.4, 1275.4, 1240.5, 1264.4 and 1116.3 ms^{-1} respectively.

At $x \sim 1.0000$ the values of experimental and theoretically predicted sound speed are same at the three investigating temperatures and the values are 1132.0, 1097.0 and 1051.6 ms^{-1} respectively.

Fig. 3 shows the deviation of theoretically evaluated sound speed values with those experimentally observed at 298 K for the ternary liquid mixture. It is attributed that Free Length Theory (FLT) is best applicable to such

Fig. 3. Deviation of theoretically predicted sound speed values [u^{FLT} (♦), u^{IDR} (■), u^{NOM} (▲), u^{VAN} (×)] from experimental values (in ms^{-1}) for heptane + 1-dodecanol + cyclohexane system at 298 K

type of ternary system without any deviation. Nomoto's Relation exhibit less deviation than Vandeaal Vangeel ideal mixing relation (VAN) which shows maximum deviation at all temperatures. All the theoretical relations applied on experimental sound speed shows positive deviation at all the three investigating temperatures. The order of deviation of various theories from experimental sound speed is as follows :

$$u^{\text{EXP}} = u^{\text{FLT}} < u^{\text{NOM}} < u^{\text{IDR}} < u^{\text{VAN}}$$

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. The densities of pure liquids and mixtures were measured using a precalibrated bicapillary pycnometer, the accuracy of data being within $\pm 0.057\%$, sound speed was measured by single crystal ultrasonic interferometer at 2 MHz frequency and data were accurate upto $\pm 0.03\%$. Viscosity was measured using Ostwald's viscometer and the accuracy fell within $\pm 0.09\%$. All measurements were made in a thermostatically controlled water bath with temperature accuracy of ± 0.1 °C. The purity of the components was ascertained from their physical constant data.

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